

THE EVOLUTION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ITS IMPACT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY

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Annotation. A strong education system is crucial to Uzbekistan’s future. For the nation to progress, it is crucial to introduce new technologies, enhance the quality of the teaching workforce, and improve the educational system.

Key words: illiteracy, comprehensive, society, International education day, qualification.

In accordance with the resolution of the General Assembly of the United Nations on December 3, 2018, January 24 was declared the International Education Day. This important decision is a clear confirmation of the importance of education for peace and development by the international community.

This year marks the fifth year of the celebration of this worldwide day. This event aims to acknowledge not only the human thirst for knowledge but also the attention of governments and societies worldwide to the challenges facing the education sector, such as the need to eradicate illiteracy and create comprehensive educational initiatives in various regions. and concentrate on matters like execution.

As UN Secretary General Antonio Guterrish stated in his video greeting on this day, one of the fundamental human rights is the right to education. [3, B. 8] However, large sums of money must be spent in order to guarantee that every person on Earth receives a high-quality education.

According to A. Guterrish education is the basis of society, economy and the potential of every person. But if investment is not attracted at the level of demand, there will be no benefit from this potential. "I am always deeply concerned that education is paid very little attention in the policies of most governments and in documents within the framework of international cooperation," said the UN Secretary

General. "The theme of this year's International Education Day is also a strong reminder of the need to give priority to education when directing investments." Investments, as A. Guterrish confidently pointed out, are of decisive importance in achieving the 4th goal in the field of sustainable development. [3, B.6]

In the last six years, an additional 500,000 student places have been created in our country, and their total number has reached 5,300,000. At present, work on creating another 1,200,000 student places is continuing rapidly. [2, B.43]

The main goal is to create the foundations of a new Renaissance - the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. It is very important that 2023 was named “Year of attention to people and quality education” in our country as part of the Development Strategy adopted for this noble goal.

Since education is the largest investment for New Uzbekistan, our state and society prioritize promoting it. The President stated that the only appropriate path for New Uzbekistan's growth is to raise the standard of education.

The education system is uniform and continuous and consists of the following types of education: preschool education and upbringing, general secondary and secondary special education, professional education, higher education, post-secondary education, personnel retraining and improving their qualifications, extracurricular education.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Pre-school Education and Training" and the Law "On Education" govern the process for setting up pre-school education and training.

Preschool education and upbringing is a type of education aimed at teaching and educating children, developing them intellectually, morally, ethically, aesthetically and physically, as well as preparing children for general secondary education. Preschool education and upbringing also includes one-year compulsory preparation of children aged six to seven years for primary education.

General secondary and secondary special education is aimed at mastering general educational programs, necessary knowledge, skills and abilities.

The stages of general secondary education	grades I-XI
basic secondary education	grades V - IX
secondary education	X - XI grades

Children are admitted to the first grade of the general secondary education organization in the year when they turn seven years old.

Importance of quality education:

- **Economic Development:** Individuals with a quality education have the ability to generate innovative ideas, adopt new technologies, and become a productive workforce.
- **Social development:** Education has a positive effect on the socio-political consciousness of a person, contributes to the development of civil society.
- **Development of human capital:** Quality education helps to develop the knowledge, skills and abilities of an individual, which increases his quality of life and opportunities to find his place in society.

Ways to develop quality education:

- **Modernization of infrastructures of educational institutions:** creation of classrooms, libraries and laboratories equipped with modern technologies.
- **Improving the qualifications of teachers:** introducing teaching methods that meet international standards, ensuring that teachers know foreign languages.
- **Democratization of the educational system:** creating opportunities for students to freely express their opinions and actively participate in their educational process.
- **Modernization of educational content:** introduction of training in modern professions that prepare students for practical life, ensuring mastery of innovative technologies [1, B.5]

In order to achieve high-quality education in Uzbekistan, a comprehensive strategy that includes curriculum reform, teacher empowerment, infrastructural development, and the promotion of a culture of lifelong learning is needed. In

addition to giving Uzbek residents the tools they need to succeed in a globalized world, this will set the stage for the country's sustained growth and prosperity.

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